

Model-Based Array Processing in a Fading Channel

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Abstract—Model-based processing is a method of including physical models in the processing scheme in order to enhance the performance (smaller error variance) of the processor. The method is based on a state-space approach which leads to Kalman type estimators. A major advantage of this approach is that the stochastic aspects of the problem (system and measurement noise) can be included in a natural way, thereby allowing modeling errors to be accommodated by the processor. In the case of array processing, one can consider several types of signal models. Indeed, in the case of a standard beamformer, the linear phase or time delay progression associated with a particular signal direction or “beam” implicitly assumes a plane wave model for the signal. However, the fact that the array is moving is not considered. It has been shown that the inclusion of the array motion in the proper way results in a significantly smaller variance on the bearing error, thereby providing a passive synthetic aperture effect. In this work the model-based method is applied to simulated towed array data in a fading channel. The amplitude of the signal, along with its source frequency and bearing are considered as the elements of a state vector to be estimated in a Kalman type estimation scheme. In this manner, the Kalman filter provides a recursive type of estimator, i.e., an adaptive processor which provides estimates of the relevant parameters, even when they are varying slowly in time. Results are shown where the data were generated with a random (Rayleigh) amplitude. The results show that the processor can track the amplitude variations and render high quality estimates of the bearing angle and source frequency, even at very low signal to noise ratios.

I. INTRODUCTION

Model-based Processing (MBP) has been shown to be a very effective technique, since it allows physical models of both signals and noise to be introduced into signal processing algorithms in a self consistent manner.¹ The approach is based on casting the problem into state-space form. There are basically two sets of equations in the MBP representation: the state equations themselves, and the measurement equa-

tions, which relate the states to the actual measured quantities. In the stochastic case, a Gauss-Markov representation evolves, which allows the inclusion of both the measurement noise and the state or “process” noise as second-order statistical models. Once this framework is established, it is possible to investigate ocean acoustic signal processing problems in a very general way, since full advantage can be taken of existing systems theory (e.g., observability, identifiability) and techniques (Kalman state estimators) to characterize a recursive processor which constitutes a minimum-variance, adaptive estimator. Recent studies have effectively applied the technique to several problems in ocean acoustics. For more information on these studies, see Reference 1 and references therein. In this study, the approach is applied to the problem of source frequency and bearing angle estimation for the case of a Rayleigh fading channel. Previous^{2,3} studies applied the technique to the problem of bearing and source frequency estimation for the case of a *deterministic* signal.

The formulation of the model is given in the next section. The third section presents results based on simulated data and the last section consists of a discussion and suggestions for future work.

II PROBLEM FORMULATION

The solution to the time dependent acoustic wave equation is any function of $t \pm x/c$, where t is time, x is position, and c is phase velocity along the x direction. For the narrow-band plane wave case, a solution can be written in complex form as

$$f(x, t) = e^{i\omega(t \pm x/c)}, \quad (1)$$

where ω is the radian frequency. Defining the state vector θ as

$$\theta = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \theta_M \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

and the so-called “plant” or system noise vector as

$$\mathbf{w} = \begin{bmatrix} w_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ w_M \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

a Gauss-Markov model can be written as

$$\frac{d}{dt}\theta(t) = \mathbf{A}(t)\theta(t) + \mathbf{w}(t), \quad (4)$$

where in this problem \mathbf{A} is the null matrix (i.e., we assume no explicit state dynamics).

A discrete recursive Kalman filter structure now can be implemented for real-time application by discretizing (4) using a finite difference approximation. This results in

$$\frac{\theta(t_k) - \theta(t_{k-1})}{\Delta t} = \mathbf{w}(t_{k-1}), \quad (5)$$

which leads immediately to the following recursive estimator.

$$\hat{\theta}(t_k|t_{k-1}) = \hat{\theta}(t_{k-1}|t_{k-1}). \quad (6)$$

That is, the bearing angles are the states and obey a random walk. (6) constitutes the recursive form of the state equation for our array processor. Letting ℓ be the hydrophone index and m be the index of the plane wave signals, the associated measurement equation is given by

$$\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}, t_k) = \begin{bmatrix} p(x_1, t_k) \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ p(x_L, t_k) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_m e^{i\omega_0 t_k + \beta_1(t_k) \sin \theta_m} \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \sum_m e^{i\omega_0 t_k + \beta_L(t_k) \sin \theta_m} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Here, $\beta_l = k_0(x_\ell + vt)$, $k_0 = \omega_0/c$ and ω_0 is the source frequency. That is, we have included the motion of the hydrophone in the measurement model. The importance of this cannot be underestimated since, as

shown by Edelson,⁴ the Cramer-Rao bound (CRB) on the variance of the bearing estimate for a moving array is significantly less than that for the same array when it is not moving. Specifically, the ratio R , of the CRB for the moving array to that of the stationary array is given by

$$R = [1 + (3/2)(D/X) + (D/X)^2]^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

where $D = vt$ is the “dynamic aperture”, i.e., the speed of motion of the array, v , times t , the processing time, and X is the physical aperture.

In our present problem, we not only desire estimates of the bearings, but also the source frequencies and the signal amplitudes. These parameters will be included in the so-called *augmented* form of the Kalman filter which will be developed in the following.

We begin by defining the *acoustic array space-time processing problem* as:

GIVEN a set of noisy pressure-field measurements and a horizontal array of L -sensors, **FIND** the “best” (minimum error variance) estimate of source bearings, temporal frequencies and amplitudes.

We choose to use the nonlinear extended Kalman filter (EKF) estimator⁵ in parameter estimation form as our MBP. We use the nonlinear pressure-field measurement model, (7), which was developed previously for M monochromatic plane wave sources. We will characterize each of the M plane wave sources by a corresponding set of temporal frequencies, bearings and amplitudes; $[\{\omega_m\}, \{\theta_m\}, \{a_m\}]$. That is,

$$p(x, t_k) = \sum_{m=1}^M a_m e^{i\omega_m t_k + \beta(t_k) \sin \theta_m} + n(t_k), \quad (9)$$

where x is the current spatial position along the x -axis in meters, v is the array speed (meter/sec), and n is additive random noise.

If we further assume, as in (7), that the single sensor equation above is expanded to include an array of L -sensors, where $x \rightarrow x_\ell$, $\ell = 1, \dots, L$, then we obtain

$$p(x_\ell, t_k) = \sum_{m=1}^M a_m e^{i\omega_m t_k + \beta_\ell(t_k) \sin \theta_m} + n_\ell(t_k). \quad (10)$$

This can be written in a more concise form as

$$\mathbf{p}(t_k) = \mathbf{c}(t_k, \Theta) + \mathbf{n}(t_k), \quad (11)$$

where the vector Θ represents the parameters of the plane wave sources and $\mathbf{p}(t_k) = [p(x_1, t_k)p(x_2, t_k), \dots, p(x_L, t_k)]^T$. Since we model these parameters as constants, the *augmented* state-space model evolves as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta(t_k) \\ \omega(t_k) \\ \mathbf{a}(t_k) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \theta(t_{k-1}) \\ \omega(t_{k-1}) \\ \mathbf{a}(t_{k-1}) \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{w}(t_{k-1}), \quad (12)$$

where $\theta := [\theta_1 \dots \theta_M]^T$, $\omega := [\omega_1 \dots \omega_M]^T$, $\mathbf{a} := [a_1 \dots a_M]^T$, and \mathbf{w} is a zero mean gaussian random vector with covariance R_{ww} .

Defining the composite parameter vector, Θ as:

$$\Theta := \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \omega \\ \mathbf{a} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

for $\Theta \in R^{3M}$, the following *augmented* state prediction equation evolves for our model-based processor.

$$\hat{\Theta}(t_k|t_{k-1}) = \hat{\Theta}(t_{k_1}|t_{k_1}), \quad (14)$$

with (11) as the associated measurement equation.

Since the state space model is linear with no explicit dynamics, the prediction relations are greatly simplified while the measurement equations become nonlinear due to the plane wave measurement model of (11). This leads to the extended Kalman filter (EKF) wherein the nonlinearities are approximated with a first-order Taylor series expansion. Here we require the measurement jacobian,⁵

$$\mathbf{C}(t_k, \Theta) := \frac{\partial \mathbf{c}(t_k, \Theta)}{\partial \Theta}, \quad (15)$$

an $L \times 3M$ matrix.

Given (11), (14) and (15), we are now in a position to compute a recursive (predictor/corrector form) extended Kalman filter estimate of the state vector Θ . The actual algorithm, although well known, is quite involved and will not be shown here in full detail, but an outline of the process is given in the following.

1. Given an initial or trial value of the state estimate, $\hat{\Theta}(t_{k-1}|t_{k-1})$, the parameter prediction equation is used to predict the value of $\hat{\Theta}(t_k|t_{k-1})$. This constitutes a prediction of the state vector for $t = t_k$ based on the data up to $t = t_{k-1}$.

2. The *innovation*, $\epsilon(t_k)$, is then computed as the difference between the new measurement taken at $t = t_k$ and the predicted measurement obtained by substituting $\hat{\Theta}(t_k|t_{k-1})$ into the measurement equation.

3. Next, the Kalman gain or weight is computed.

4. The Kalman gain is then used in the correction stage, producing $\hat{\Theta}(t_k|t_k)$, the corrected estimate.

5. This corrected estimate is then substituted into the right hand side of the prediction equation, thereby initiating the next iteration.

A more complete description of the EKF algorithm can be found in Reference 5.

This completes the discussion of the model-based array processor. In the next section we will present some examples based on synthesized data.

III PERFORMANCE EXAMPLES

In this section we present some results on a single plane wave example. Thus, the state vector defined in (13) simplifies to a three dimensional vector consisting of a single bearing angle, a single frequency and a single amplitude. Furthermore, the data are synthesized with a Rayleigh amplitude in order to simulate a fading channel. The Rayleigh amplitude was generated from two Gaussians which were passed through a Butterworth filter. This allowed the characteristic time of the amplitude variation to be determined by the cutoff frequency of the filter.

In the following example, a four element array with an element spacing of 15 meters is receiving a 50Hz signal at a bearing of 45 degrees. The array is moving at a speed of 5 meters/second. The synthetic data were generated with a characteristic (Rayleigh) fading time of approximately 20 seconds and a nominal signal to noise ratio of -13 dB at the hydrophone level. The data were sampled at 250 Hz, i.e., 2.5 times the Nyquist rate. The initial values of the pa-

rameters were taken to be 40 degrees, 50.1 Hz and .05 for the bearing, source frequency and amplitude, respectively.

Figure 1 shows the variation of the simulated amplitude variation over the processing time of 30 seconds. In comparison to Fig.1, Fig.2 shows the estimated amplitude. As can be seen in this illustration the estimated amplitude lags the true value somewhat, as might be expected. Figures 3 and 4 show, respectively, the estimated bearing and source frequency. Here it is seen that, in spite of the low signal to noise ratio, these estimates are quite good.

IV DISCUSSION

This work has demonstrated the effectiveness of the state-space approach to bearing and source frequency estimation. As mentioned previously, the source frequency and bearing estimation problem has been solved for the narrow band deterministic case,^{2,3} where here, the formulation has been extended to the random amplitude case. the next logical step is to generalize the approach to the broad band case. This could be done as a parallel set of narrow band processors, but this would probably be too computationally intensive. A more tractable approach would be to characterize the signal as an autoregressive moving average (ARMA) model. In this approach, the parameters of the ARMA model will be estimated simultaneously with the signal bearing(s). The advantage of this approach is that the ARMA model can be tailored to particular classes of signals. That is, classes of signals with particular spectral characteristics.

One interesting aspect of the results is the superior quality of the bearing and frequency estimates as compared to the amplitude estimate. This is an important result, since for our purposes, the amplitude is actually a nuisance parameter, playing the role of a scaling factor. This is interesting for another reason, since the scale factor will be a parameter in any ARMA process that would be used as a broad band signal model. What this implies is that it will probably be the autoregressive part of the ARMA model that will play the most important role in modeling the spectrum of the actual signal.

Figure 1: Simulated Rayleigh Amplitude

Figure 2: Estimated Rayleigh Amplitude

References

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Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the Naval Undersea Warfare Center's Independent Research Program. The program manager is Dr. Stuart Dickenson.

Figure 3: Estimated Bearing Angle

Figure 4: Estimated Source Frequency